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Unbiased discovery of genes required for pluripotency: Terf1.

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Qualities of the stem cells of the embryo or the gametes include pluripotency and totipotency. Pluripotency as a quality that defines the embryonic stem cell is likely a process or entity distinguishable from the multi-lineage differentiation capacity that defines the HSC. We separated hematopoietic stem and embryonic stem programs for blind discovery of pluripotency-associated factors in the ES cell. We describe identification of Terf1 as a factor regulating or associated with pluripotency in the human embryonic stem cell.

Citations

1. Van Steensel, B. and De Lange, T., 1997. Control of telomere length by the human telomeric protein TRF1. Nature, 385(6618), pp.740-743.